

Effect of chemical seed treatments on productivity of upland rice

C. Kundu and S. Biswas, Rice Research Station, Chinsurah, India

Studies at the College of Agriculture, Calcutta University, showed that soaking stored seeds of various crops in water or solutions of certain chemicals for 2 to 3 h followed by drying greatly minimized the loss of vigor and viability during subsequent storage under natural conditions. We evaluated the hydration-dehydration seed treatment with and without chemicals and dry-dressing with calcium peroxide for improving yield of upland rice.

Five-month-old IR50 and CR237-1 seeds were soaked for 2.5 h in water or chemical solutions of different concentrations and then dried to their original weight. Seeds were dry-dressed in the calcium peroxide treatment. The experi-

Effect of seed treatment on rice growth and yield, Chinsurah, India, 1983.

Treatment	Panicles/m ²		Yield (t/ha)	
	CR237-1	IR50	CR237-1	IR50
Control	377	441	2.5	2.2
Water	405	472	2.7	2.5
Disodium phosphate (2 × 10 ⁻³ M)	426	510	3.0	2.7
Sodium chloride (5 × 10 ⁻³ M)	438	539	3.1	2.8
Potassium meta bisulfide (5 × 10 ⁻³ M)	419	490	2.9	2.5
Calcium peroxide (100 mg of CaO ₂ /g of seed)	414	464	2.9	2.5
Ethephon (10 ppm)	452	531	3.1	2.0
CD (0.05)	28		0.2 t/ha	

ment was under strict rainfed conditions in a randomized block design with three replications. Varieties were direct-seeded in lines at 20-cm between-row spacing.

The treatments significantly increased the number of panicles/m² and yield of both varieties (see table). The sodium

chloride treatment was best, followed by ethephon. Both treatments were significantly better than hydration alone. Simple hydration increased yield about 10% over the untreated control. The physicochemical basis of the beneficial effects is not yet understood. □

Efficiency of modified-urea materials applied at different N levels in lowland rice in the Cuu Long Delta

B. K. Singh, Pham Sy Tan, and Nguyen Thi Thu Hong, Cuu Long Delta Rice Research Center, Oman, Hau Giang, S. R. Vietnam

In 1983 wet season, we evaluated the

Effect of modified-urea materials, applied at varying N rates, on grain yield and yield attributes of rice at Oman, Vietnam, 1983 wet season.

N level (kg/ha)	Form of urea material	Panicles/m ²	Spikelets/panicle	Unfilled spikelets (%)	1,000-grain wt (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)
0 (control)	None	256	62	17	26	3.1
	PU	293	68	17	27	3.6
	SCU	309	73	19	27	4.4
	USG	311	72	20	27	4.3
58	PU	304	71	20	27	3.9
	SCU	339	72	25	27	4.1
	USG	342	74	22	27	4.1
87	PU	349	73	22	27	4.3
	SCU	347	73	26	27	3.8
	USG	346	76	24	26	3.9
116	PU	357	70	27	28	3.9
	SCU	356	73	28	28	3.8
	USG	345	71	27	27	3.7
LSD (0.05)		41	9	7	NS	0.5

^aPU = prilled urea, SCU = sulfur-coated urea, USG = urea supergranules.

efficiency of prilled urea (PU), sulfur-coated urea (SCU), and urea supergranules (USG) at 29, 58, 87, and 116 kg N/ha in lowland transplanted rice in a randomized complete block design with 3 replications. A no-N control was included to compute the efficiency of the treatments. The soil of the experimental plot was clayey with 0.18% total N, 0.04% total P, 0.77 meq Al³⁺/100 g soil, and

pH 4.6. Twenty-eight-d-old seedlings of early-maturing OM33 were transplanted on 1 Aug 1983 at 20 × 20-cm spacing using 2 seedlings/hill. All plots received 18 kg P/ha as superphosphate at transplanting. PU was broadcast in 2 splits: 2/3 at transplanting + 1/3 at panicle initiation. SCU was broadcast at transplanting, and USG was placed 8-10 cm deep in the center of 4 hills in alternate rows 6 d after transplanting. The soil was flooded from transplanting to maturity. The crop was harvested on 27 Oct 1983.

At 29 kg N/ha, rice yields with SCU and USG were similar and significantly superior to those with PU (see table). At 58, 67, and 116 kg N/ha, PU, SCU, and USG did not differ significantly. Applying 29 kg N/ha as SCU or USG gave a yield response similar to that with 87 kg N/ha as PU. We observed a decreasing trend in grain yield with SCU and USG after 29 kg N/ha. With PU, yield increased to 87 kg N/ha and was significantly higher than that obtained with 29 kg N/ha. Plant height, spikelets/panicle, and 1,000-grain weight were not affected by N sources. Panicles/m² increased with increasing N supply. Reduced grain yield